

Exploring the Trajectory of Educators' Emotional Intelligence in TVET Curriculum Delivery: A Study of the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro

Iro-Idoro, Charlotte Bose¹ & Jimoh, Tajudeen Adisa²

1,2. Office Technology and Management Department, The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria.
Email: ²orjeebasit@gmail.com, ²tajudeen.jimoh@federalpolyilaro.edu.ng
ORCID: ²0000-0002-6931-3369

Abstract

Educators play a pivotal role in the effective delivery of curriculum leading to the acquisition of skills and knowledge. Beyond qualification and technical expertise, educators' emotional intelligence has emerged as a significant factor shaping the quality of instruction, student motivation, and learning effectiveness. This study examines the influence of emotional intelligence on TVET curriculum delivery among educators in the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro. Survey design was adopted and the population comprised all educators of TVET based courses in the Institution. A 4-point likert questionnaire was developed as instrument of data collection and administered on a sample of 100 TVET educators selected using multi-stage technique. Data collected were analysed with inferential statistics involving regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance on SPSS Version 25. The results showed that the domain of emotional intelligence covered (Self-awareness, self-emotional control and empathy) have significant influence on curriculum delivery among the TVET educators in the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro. It was therefore concluded that emotional intelligence is an important characteristic of educators which portends significant bearing on methods, approach and effectiveness of curriculum delivery. The study recommends, among others, that educators in TVET-based courses in the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro should regularly make conscious effort toward portraying good level of emotional intelligence in their teaching and relationship with students.

Keywords: *Curriculum Delivery, Emotional Intelligence, Empathy, Self-Awareness, Self-Emotional Control, TVET Educators.*

1. BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Globally, polytechnics and other technical tertiary institutions are responsible for the development of technical and vocational capacities that are necessary for self-reliance and economic sustenance of individuals and for technological, economic and social development of a country and her societies.

In Nigeria, the need for functional, relevant and practical training at tertiary level to facilitate the development of competencies for individuals to be productive, earn a living and contribute to the national development stimulates the attention and importance attributed to Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programmes and career (Iro-idoro & Jimoh, 2021). The essence of TVET programmes to provide the growing population of developing and underdeveloped nations with knowledge and skills capable of giving them opportunity for technical skill acquisition and utilisation, job creation and economic self-reliance (UNESCO, 2021). It centres on equipping the recipients with practical skills and knowledge for a specific trade or vocation, to complement the generic education (Pradhan, 2023). While its specific goals vary depending on the needs of a society and its local market demands, in general, it offers youths the opportunity for employment and productive

engagement through workable blends of formal, informal, and non-formal learning (Paryono, 2017; UNESCO, 2021).

The effectiveness of education programmes, according to Rauner (2009), depends on the implementation of curricula and their delivery is one of the key areas of educators' characteristics requiring attention. The description, nature, objectives, learning goals, methods, tools aids, requirement and teaching of any subject or theme in a course of study are usually embedded in the curriculum of such subjects as a matter of regulation and control (Su, 2012). According to Ofor-Douglas (2020), a curriculum is a collection of thoughtfully selected and organized materials that are intended to accomplish a certain learning objective and are judged adequate to fulfill the functional demands of a people in a specific time and place. It is also defined as all educational opportunities and experiences, including tools and a carefully organized timetable for the student under the institution's supervision, with the intention of modifying the student's behavior in the environment (Oladosu, 2014).

The importance of curriculum in education gives credence to the significance of effective, efficient and functional curriculum delivery. Curriculum delivery is a tactic that aids educators and students in reaching their objectives through a variety of procedures, including instruction, mentorship, counsel, guidance, and engagement; it also fosters participatory and collaborative learning and the development of reasoning abilities. According to Vidya (2015), curriculum delivery also involves assessment, counseling, and feedback. According to Kelly (2018), teachers' roles, attitudes, and characteristics in the curriculum-building process should help students make connections between the curriculum's goals and content. This provides educators with the opportunity to be creative and infuse their unique style into the way that pupils learn.

When it comes to the tertiary TVET curriculum, the educators are considered the primary facilitator of the curriculum implementation process. Delivery and implementation of the curriculum refer to how the educator chooses and combines the several subjects covered in a syllabus or curriculum document based on his or her own qualifications, abilities and disposition (Ayonmike, 2014). Thus, curriculum delivery occurs when students interact with the teacher, the learning resources, the learning environment, and the syllabus that the teacher created (Chaudhary, 2015).

Polytechnics in Nigeria are particularly saddled with the mandate for developing competencies, skills and abilities in technical-oriented courses and programmes of study. The teaching and learning requirements, processes and goals of science, technology, engineering, mathematics and management subjects in polytechnics are embedded in the curriculum of studies for individual programmes. Effective delivery of curriculum leading to the acquisition of skills and knowledge in TVET courses is expected to equip learners with functional capabilities to be significant contributors to social, economic and technological development of the nation. However, several characteristics and traits of educators interact in the process of curriculum implementation and delivery which are deemed to have far-reaching impacts on the quality, modality and coverage of the curriculum (Chaudhary, 2015; Kachingwe & Nithyanantham, 2023). One of such factors and educators-based characteristics is emotional intelligence which researchers have found to be significant in the attitude, disposition and major outcomes of many job roles. In view of the multifaceted issues confronted by educators and instructors in the teaching process, the need to provide for individual difference among learners, and the importance of teachers' abilities to combine cognitive and non-cognitive competence in teaching and learning processes, an examination of the influence of emotional

intelligence of TVET educators on the effectiveness of curriculum delivery is deemed relevant and worthwhile.

In tertiary institutions (polytechnic, universities and colleges), teachers face many social expectations and demands from students (Hassan et al., 2015) and encounter a number of issues – “negative emotions including strain, aggression, hopelessness and frustration” (Ismail, et al., 2009) in the teaching of the curriculum content which regularly require them to bring to not only cognitive aspect of competence but also non-cognitive psychological aspect called emotional intelligence (Shazia et al., 2018). Emotional intelligence has been supported in many empirical findings to be an important predictor of various enviable organizational outcomes, such as performance, job satisfaction, organizational citizenship behaviour, service delivery, curriculum implementation delivery organizational commitment (Steve, 2014; Goleman, 2014). Emotional intelligence is the aptitude, capacity, talent, or self-perceived ability to recognize, evaluate, and control one's own emotions as well as those of others and groups. Individuals with high emotional intelligence use the understanding of their own emotion to define the emotions of others. They are upbeat, robust, and persistent in handling the emotions of others (Tripathy, 2018).

Many factors capable of enhancing emotional intelligence of an individual are also known to lessen stress and, consequently foster harmony among groups in organizations. These components include regulating conflict, creating connections and understanding, and promoting stability, continuity, and harmony (Icaew, 2021). According to Lam (2016), emotional and social competences and skills are presented as emotional intelligence in order to support intelligent behavior. It can also be defined as the capacity to assess and control feelings (Quoidbach & Hansenne, 2013). In addition to managing their own emotions, emotionally intelligent individuals are able to solve problems and make wise decisions (Mayer et al., 2014).

Emotional Intelligence and its specific dimensions have been attributed to success in the teaching role (Lam, 2016) and occupational success, group decision, interpersonal communication, etc. (Hejase, et al., 2012; Icaew, 2021). Several dimensions gave birth to different elements and metrics employed in describing emotional intelligence (hejase et al., 2012; Quoidbach & Hansenne, 2013). This study considers the Goleman (1998) model of emotional intelligence comprising “self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and relationship management” and adopts self-awareness, managing emotions, self-motivation and empathy as measure of emotional intelligence of TVET educators.

Self-awareness refers to the ability of an individual to identify his own feelings, comprehend own typical emotional reactions to situations, and having acknowledge of how one's behaviour, activities and dispositions are affected by emotion. Being self-aware means that you have a clear understanding of your own strengths and weaknesses and can see yourself as others do. The ability to maintain calmness, composure and reason rationally in the face of severe feelings is a necessary component of *emotion management*. Being able to control your emotions will help you accept accountability for your actions and prevent you from making rash judgments that you may come to regret. Using your strongest feelings to propel and direct yourself toward your objectives is known as *self-motivation*. This ability enables an individual to take the initiative and to persevere in the face of obstacles and setbacks. The capacity to see, comprehend, and react to the emotions of others is referred to as empathy. Being self-aware is a prerequisite for empathy. You cannot read the emotions of people if you are unaware of your own feelings (Hejase, et al., 2012; Lam, 2016; Hejase, 2018; Icaew, 2021).

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The broad objective of this study was to examine the influence of emotional intelligence domains on TVET curriculum delivery among educators in the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro. The specific objectives were to:

- Determine the influence of educators' self-awareness on TVET curriculum delivery
- Investigate the extent to which educators' self-emotional management facilitates TVET curriculum delivery; and
- Determine the extent to which educators' empathy contributes to effective curriculum delivery in TVET.

3. METHODOLOGY

Survey approach was adopted in collecting data for this study. The population comprised 233 academic staff in TVET related programmes of the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro at the time of this study. The Polytechnic has six schools (faculties) out of which five are fully grounded in TVET-based programmes. These are Schools Agriculture, Communication and Information Technology, Engineering, Environmental Studies and Pure and Applied Sciences.

A total of 100 educators in the TVET related disciplines of was selected through a multi-stage sampling process. In the first instance, faculties offering TVET-based courses were identified, then 20 educators were allocated for selection from each of the five schools (faculties), and were randomly selected and covered in the survey.

In line with the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 95% confidence interval:

H₀₁: There will be no significant influence of self-awareness on TVET curriculum delivery among educators.

H₀₂: There will be no significant influence of self-emotional control on TVET curriculum delivery among educators.

H₀₃: There will be no significant influence of empathy on TVET curriculum delivery among educators.

A four-point likert questionnaire was used for data collection. Items on Emotional Intelligence scale were adapted from Mehta & Singh (2013) Emotional Intelligence Scale and factor input for Curriculum Delivery were adapted from Quality of Teaching in Higher Education Questionnaire of Organisation for Economic and Cooperative Development (2019).

Out of 100 questionnaires administered, 96 were completed and returned by the respondents. Given the nature of the data, all analyses were conducted via SPSS Version 25 statistical software. Hypotheses formulated were tested with regression statistics at 0.05 level of significance.

4. RESULTS

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of self-awareness on TVET curriculum delivery among Educators in the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro.

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.685 ^a	.265	.269	.18723

a. Predictors: (Constant), SA

The model summarizing the statistical relationship of self-awareness and curriculum delivery is depicted in the above table. The table shows a moderately strong positive relationship between self-awareness and curriculum delivery with correlation coefficient of 0.685 which illustrates that about 26% of the total variation in curriculum delivery could be attributed to self-awareness.

Table 2: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	.086	1	.086	.678	.001 ^b
	Residual	11.995	94	.128		
	Total	12.082	95			

a. Dependent Variable: CD
b. Predictors: (Constant), SA

As shown above, with P-value of $0.001 < 0.05$ threshold of significance, the model used to relate self-awareness with curriculum delivery is considered statistically adequate for the test.

Table 3: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.190	.506		8.283	.000
	SA	.210	.133	.245	3.823	.001 ^b

a. Dependent Variable: CD

Table 3 reveals the co-efficient of influence of self-awareness on curriculum delivery. The result shows a p-value of $0.001 < 0.05$ indicating that self-awareness has significant influence on curriculum delivery. As depicted in the result, a unit change in self-awareness will yield about 21 unit change ($B=0.210$) in curriculum delivery by the respondents. At t-value of 3.283 and significant value of 0.001 which is less than 0.05 level of significance, we reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternative hypotheses. Thus, it is upheld that there is significant influence of self-awareness on curriculum delivery among TVET educators in the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro.

The result indicates a significant influence of self-awareness on curriculum delivery. The result points to the fact that self-awareness as a domain of emotional intelligence impact on the effectiveness of teaching and TVET curriculum delivery in terms of coverage of curriculum content, practical skill impartation, educators' engagement of students and participation, provision of feedback on individual student's performance, provision of study materials and in guiding the students. It was found that the ability of the educators to be aware of their own feelings and how it may affect their performance and others, knowing personal weaknesses and strength and being open to learning will help in their efforts and activities in teaching and achievement of curriculum goals. The finding corroborates Lam (2016) and Hejase (2018) that self-awareness and other specific domains of emotional Intelligence have been linked to success in teaching and effectiveness of curriculum delivery.

The finding presents a vivid importance of self-awareness of educators in the teaching of TVET courses. This clearly shows the need for TVET educators and instructors to be consciously aware of their state of emotion and what such emotional state portends in the delivery of curriculum content and the development of technical and vocations skills of the students.

H0₂: There is no significant influence of self-emotional control on TVET curriculum delivery among Educators in the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.481 ^a	.231	.237	.18723

a. Predictors: (Constant), SEC

Table 4 shows the model summary for the statistical relationship of self-emotional control and curriculum delivery. The result portrays a positive relationship between the variables ($r =$ of 0.481) and that 23% of the total variation in curriculum delivery could be linked to self-emotional control.

Table 5: ANOVA

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.086	1	.086	.678	.003 ^b
	Residual	11.995	94	.128		
	Total	12.082	95			

a. Dependent Variable: CD
b. Predictors: (Constant), SEC

As shown in the ANOVA table above, P-value of 0.001 is significantly less than 0.05 threshold of significance. This indicates that the model used to relate self-emotional control with curriculum delivery is statistically adequate for the test.

Table 6: Coefficients^a

		Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.190	.506		6.113	.000
	SEC	.180	.133	.185	3.314	.003

a. Dependent Variable: CD

Table 6 gives the co-efficient of the influence of the independent variable (self-emotional control) on the dependent variable (curriculum delivery). The result shows a p-value of $0.003 < 0.05$ indicating that self-emotional control has significant influence on curriculum delivery. As depicted in the result, a unit change in self-emotional control will yield about 18unit change ($B=0.180$) in curriculum delivery by the respondents. Hence, at t-value = 3.314 and p value = $0.003 < 0.05$, it is upheld that self-emotional control has significant influence on TVET curriculum delivery among educators in the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro.

The result indicates a significant influence of the predictor variable (self-emotional control) on curriculum delivery. It was found that the ability of individual TVET educator to know clearly his happy and sad moods, wining over the sad mood, being composed, organised and calm in the face of frustration and making effort to think clearly, to stay focused and avoid temptations are important to effectively reaching the goal of curriculum of the subjects being handled. The finding is in line with Icaew (2021) that being able to control one's emotion

enables one to avoid hasty decision helps in taking good initiative when confronted with obstacles and setbacks in the course of discharge responsibilities.

The above finding gives a clear pointer to the importance of self-emotional control and management in the teaching of TVET courses. When educators are able to control their emotion and do not allow their personal and intrinsic issues to override their focus in the teaching of TVET students, the achievement of the short and long-term goals of teaching technical and vocational courses will be greatly enhanced. The implication of this is that adequate and quality coverage of curriculum in each TVET disciplined goes a long way in achieving technical and vocation skill development among learners.

H0₃: There is no significant influence of empathy on TVET curriculum delivery among Educators in the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro.

Table 7: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.404 ^a	.163	.169	.35099

a. Predictors: (Constant), E

Table 7 shows the model summary of the statistical relationship between empathy and curriculum delivery. The result indicates that there is a positive relationship between the variables as shown in the correlation coefficient of 0.404. The result also indicates that about 16% of the total variation in curriculum delivery among the respondents could be attributed to empathy.

Table 8: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	.502	1	.502	4.072	.006 ^b
	Residual	11.580	94	.123		
	Total	12.082	95			

a. Dependent Variable: CD

b. Predictors: (Constant), E

From the above, the model used to relate empathy with curriculum delivery is statistically adequate (P-value = 0.006 < 0.05).

Table 9: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	2.716	.526		5.167	.000
	E	.282	.140	.204	2.018	.006

a. Dependent Variable: CD

Table 9 gives the co-efficient of the influence of the independent variable (empathy) on the dependent variable (curriculum delivery). The result shows a p-value of 0.006 < 0.05 indicating that empathy has significant influence on curriculum delivery.

As depicted in the result, a unit change in empathy will yield about 28unit change (B=0.282) in curriculum delivery by the respondents. At t-value of 2.018 and P-value 0.006 < 0.05, it is upheld that empathy has significant influence on TVET curriculum delivery among educators in the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study examined the influence of emotional intelligence of TVET Curriculum Delivery in the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria. Focus was put on three domains of emotional intelligence (self-awareness, self-emotional control and empathy) with a view to determining their influence of TVET curriculum delivery.

The first specific objective of this study was to assess the influence of self-awareness on TVET curriculum delivery among educators in the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro. The result points to the fact that self-awareness as a domain of emotional intelligence impact on the effectiveness of teaching and TVET curriculum delivery in terms of coverage of curriculum content, practical skill impartation, educators' engagement of students and participation, provision of feedback on individual student's performance, provision of study materials and in guiding the students. It was found that the ability of the educators to be aware of their own feelings and how it may affect their performance and others, knowing personal weaknesses and strength and being open to learning will help in their efforts and activities in teaching and achievement of curriculum goals. The finding corroborates Lam (2016) and Hejase (2018) that self-awareness and other specific domains of emotional Intelligence have been linked to success in teaching and effectiveness of curriculum delivery.

The finding gives the vivid importance of self-awareness of educators in the teaching of TVET courses. This clearly shows the need for TVET educators and instructors to be consciously aware of their state of emotion and what such emotional state portends in the delivery of curriculum content and the development of technical and vocations skills of the students.

On the second objective, the result indicates a significant influence of the predictor variable (self-emotional control) on curriculum delivery by the TVET educators. It was found that the ability of individual TVET educator to know clearly his happy and sad moods, wining over the sad mood, being composed, organised and calm in the face of frustration and making effort to think clearly, to stay focused and avoid temptations are important to effectively reaching the goal of curriculum of the subjects being handled. The finding is in line with Icaew (2021) that being able to control one's emotion enables one to avoid hasty decision helps in taking good initiative when confronted with obstacles and setbacks in the course of discharge responsibilities.

The above finding gives a clear pointer to the importance of self-emotional control and management in the teaching of TVET courses. When educators are able to control their emotion and do not allow their personal and intrinsic issues to override their focus in the teaching of TVET students, the achievement of the short and long-term goals of teaching technical and vocational courses will be greatly enhanced. The implication of this is that adequate and quality coverage of curriculum in each TVET disciplined goes a long way in achieving technical and vocation skill development among learners.

From the test of null hypothesis 3 postulated in pursuance of the third objective of this study, it was revealed that being empathy is significantly important in the processes of TVET curriculum delivery. It is clearly shown that having a clear knowledge of differences in the feeling and thinking of the TVET students, understanding students' points of view and submissions, relating well with them, putting oneself in the position of the students, understanding verbal and non-verbal communication appropriately will be greatly instrumental in reaching TVET teaching objectives and delivering the curriculum appropriately.

The findings of this study portends the importance of emotional intelligence of educators in implementing the object of curriculum especially in the context of technical and vocational education and training of tertiary institutions. The implication of this is that, beyond technical and vocations skill competence of educators, consideration for the engagement of educators for teaching of technical and vocation subjects should emphasize remarkable portrayal of emotional intelligence by the educators. The possession and exhibition of such emotional intelligence will not only enhance quality instruction and teaching of TVET courses but will also engender teaching of same intelligence to students through manifestation and knowledge transfer in the learning process.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examines the influence of emotional intelligence on curriculum delivery among lecturers in TVET-based courses in the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro. From the result, it is concluded that the domains of emotional intelligence examined in this study (self-awareness, self-emotional control and empathy) are essential human characteristics that have bearings on how educators in TVET programmes and courses reach the objective of curriculum delivery in the Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro. Being empathic is an important personal characteristic of educators which will assist in identifying and providing for individual differences in learners and in relating with them compassionately in the process of teaching and knowledge impartation.

Based on the above conclusion, it is recommended that educators and instructors of TVET courses in the Federal Polytechnic Ilaro should regularly make conscious effort at exhibiting good level of emotional intelligence in their teaching and relationship with students; management of the institutions should organise periodic training members of academic staff with special focus on emotional intelligence; and heads of departments and supervisory units of polytechnics and other tertiary institutions should, as a matter of supervisory and social support, pay attention to stressful situations and frustrating moments being faced by academic staff members in their units.

References

- 1) Akanwa, U. N. & Kalu-Uche, N. (2015). Women in STEM: Closing the gender gap to national transformation. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME) Volume 5, Issue 2 Ver. III, PP 08-15* www.iosrjournals.org DOI: 10.9790/7388-05230815 www.iosrjournals.org 8.
- 2) Asunda, P. A. (2014). A Conceptual Framework for STEM Integration into Curriculum Through Career and Technical Education. *Journal of STEM Teacher Education, 49(1)*
- 3) Chaudhary, G. K. (2015). Factors affecting curriculum implementation for students. *International Journal of Applied Research 2015; 1(12), 984-986.*
- 4) Goleman, D. (2014). *Primal Leadership: Realizing the Power of Emotional Intelligence.* Boston: Harvard Business School.
- 5) Hassan, F., Chew, B. & Zain, A.M. & (2015). The relationship between the social management of emotional intelligence and academic performance among medic
- 6) Hejase, H. J. (2018). Emotional Intelligence. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.19447.32169

- 7) Hejase, H. J., Al-Sayed, S., Haddad, Z. & Hamdar, B. (2012). Applying Emotional Intelligence in Lebanon: An Exploratory Study. *Universal Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 2(6).
- 8) Icaew, I. (2021). The 5 elements of emotional intelligence. <https://www.icaew.com/insights/student-insights/the-5-elements-of-emotional-intelligence>
- 9) Iro-Idoro, C. B. & Jimoh, T. A. (2020). Empowering youths for self-reliance through technical and vocational education and training. *Journal of Women in Technical Education and Employment*, 1(2), 86-95. <https://fpwitedjournal.federalpolyilaro.edu.ng>
- 10) Iro-idoro, C.B. & Jimoh, T. A. (2021) TVET, empowerment and poverty alleviation among women in Ogun State, Nigeria. *International Journal for Research in Social Science and Humanities*, 7(11), 1-8.
- 11) Ismail, A., Suh, Y. S., Ajis, M. N. E., & Dollah, N. F. (2009). Relationship between occupational stress, emotional intelligence and job performance: An Empirical Study in Malaysia. *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, 10(539), 3-16.
- 12) Kachingwe, C. & Nithyanantham, V. (2023). Examining factors affecting curriculum implementation in achieving high academic performance in Malawi – A case study of Kadzkalowa Community Day Secondary School. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 6(5), 2966-2975. DOI: 10.47191/ijcsrr/V6-i5-35.
- 13) Kelly, S. M. (2018). Role of Teachers in the Curriculum Process. <https://work.chron.com/role-teachers-curriculum-process-5344.html>.
- 14) Lam, K. (2016). *Studies in Emotional Intelligence. Redefine our approach to leadership development*. Public Personnel Management, Liverpool: Goodness Publisher.
- 15) Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P., Caruso, D. R. (2014). Models of Emotional Intelligence. *University of Mauritius Research Journal*, 27, 361-372.
- 16) Mehta S. & Singh, N. (2013). Development of the Emotional Intelligence Scale. *International Journal of Management & Information Technology*, Vol. 8, No. 1 www.cirworld.com,
- 17) Morgan, J. P. (2020). STEM in TVET Curriculum. *ILO Technical Education and Skills Development Authority Guide*. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_emp/---ifp_skills/documents/publication/wcms_776446.pdf
- 18) Ofor-Douglas, S. (2020). Implementation and quality delivery services in Nigerian Universities. *African Journal of Educational Archives*, 6(1), 1-13.
- 19) Organisation for Economic and Cooperative Development (2019). Quality Teaching in Higher Education: Individual Review. <https://www.oecd.org/ducation/imhe/44144544.pdf>.
- 20) Paryono, P. (2017). The importance of TVET and its contribution to sustainable development. Proceedings of the Green Construction and Engineering Education Conference. DOI:10.1063/1.5003559.

- 21) Pradhan, H. (2023). The Benefits of TVET: Why Technical and Vocational Education and Training is a Smart Choice. <https://tvetjournal.com/tvet-systems/benefits-of-tvet>.
- 22) Quoidbach, L. & Hansenne, R. (2013). Linking emotional intelligence, spirituality and workplace performance: Definition, Models and Ideas for Research. *Journal of Managerial Psychology, Teaching and Teacher Education*, 28, 750-759.
- 23) Rauner, F. (2009). Overview: TVET Curriculum Development and Delivery. In: Maclean, R., Wilson, D. (eds) *International Handbook of Education for the Changing World of Work*. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-5281-1_106
- 24) Shazia, K., Mohammad S. & Hafiz, M. I. (2018). Emotional intelligence of lecturers and its impact on teaching effectiveness at public universities of Peshawar. *Global Regional Review*, 3(1). Doi.org/10.31703/grr.2018(III-I).31
- 25) Steve, L. (2014). How Emotional Intelligence Can Improve Management Performance. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 28, 750-759.
- 26) Su, S. W. (2012). The various concepts of curriculum and the factors involved in curricula-making. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 3(1), 153-158.
- 27) Tripathy, M. (2018). Emotional intelligence: An overview. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335433492>.
- 28) UNESCO (2021). Sub-education policy review report: Technical and vocational education and training. <https://en.unesco.org>.
- 29) Vidya, B. M. (2015). Curriculum delivery, policy and procedure. https://www.vbmv.org/pdf/iqac/Curriculum_Delivery.pdf
- 30) Wu, Y. T. & Anderson O. R. (2015) Technology-enhanced stem (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) Education. *Journal of Computers in Education*, 2(3). 10.1007/s40692-015-0041-2
- 31) Ayonmike, C. S. (2014). Challenges in Implementing the TVET Curriculum in Technical Colleges in Southern Nigeria. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*, 6(1) 87 – 97. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/majohe.v6i1.5>